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A fatty acid intake defect in the foam cell.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The foam cell transcriptome was defined by silencing of lipase A and loss of methylsterol monooxygenase (MSMO1) together with activation of the superoxide dismutase SOD2.